

PERSONALITY TRAITS AND SOCIAL SKILLS AMONG COLLEGE STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

The goal of schools and universities is to make graduates ready for a collaborative work environment. The study was conducted to identify which domain of parenting behavior best predict the personality traits of college students. Descriptive correlation method of research was used in the study. The study was conducted among 150 students' college students in the University of Southeastern Philippines, College of Development Management. Based on the findings, the researcher concluded the level of parenting behavior of parents is high and the level of personality traits of the college students is also high. There is a significant relationship between parenting behavior of parents and personality traits of the college students.

KEYWORDS:

Personality Traits, Social Skills, College Students, Descriptive correlation design, Philippines

INTRODUCTION

To achieve the goal of making work-ready graduates, schools and universities must tackle a challenge: prepare their graduates for a collaborative work environment. In recent years, the world has seen a rise in the demand for collaboration and collaborative communication (Kerravala, 2017). The rise of digital tools for communication has allowed the modern workplace to evolve and collaborate. In order to meet the demand for collaboration, prospect graduates must possess a high level of social skills.

Similarly, a high level of social skills has also been linked to the success of entrepreneurs. Baron & Markman (2000) have argued that social skills are valuable to entrepreneurs as it helps them develop the needed social capital, reputation, and professional relationships that can get them access to venture capitalists, potential customers, and other people that will be of benefit to their business. Another study (Baron & Jintong, 2009) has confirmed the link between an entrepreneur's social skills and the performance of a new venture business. Thus, it is imperative that schools and universities must hone the social skills of their learners. This will equip them with the tools that they will need whether they decide to enter into the job market or build their own business. Numerous studies have explored personality traits and social skills as independent variables. One study has attempted to establish personality and social skills as a determinant of psychopathological disorder (Landazabal, 2014). This study established a link between a deficit in social skills and the personality traits of neuroticism as an indicator of psychopathological disorder. A study of Bartholomeu, da Silva Nunes & Machado (2008) studied that relationship between social skills and personality traits, focusing on the agreeableness trait based on the Big Five model, with college students as their subjects. The results of their study recommend that the personality traits determine different aspects of social skills. Another study by Morgeson, Reider & Campion (2005) used both personality and social skills as an indicator of teamwork knowledge to help advice human resource managers on how personality can be a determinant of an applicant's fit in a teamwork or collaborative environment.

This study attempts to contribute to the existing literature by attempting to empirically establish the relationship of personality traits as an independent variable with social skills as a dependent variable. Furthermore, with the SHS in its infancy stages, which has only been established in the school year 2012-2013 (Quismondo, 2012), the study hopes to assists in the development of future curricula and teaching strategies which can help to enhance the social skills of SHS learners, and ultimately help increase their chances of success whether graduates choose to enter the job market or build their own business. This study contributes to the body of researches specific to the unique situation of SHS today.

OBJECTIVE

The study was conducted to identify which domain of parenting behavior best predict the personality traits of college students.

METHODOLOGY

Descriptive correlation method of research was used in the study. The goal is the acquisition of factual a systematic data that can be used in averages, frequencies and similar statistical calculations. The study was conducted among 150 students' college students in the University of Southeastern Philippines, College of Development Management. Mean, standard deviation, correlation and linear regression were the statistical tools used for the data analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONTable 1. *Level of Parenting Behavior of Parents*

Indicator	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Warmth	0.51	4.01	High
Rejection	0.65	3.90	High
Structure	0.90	4.12	High
Chaos	0.78	4.00	High
Autonomy Support	0.71	4.07	High
Coercion	1.01	3.53	High
Overall	0.51	3.94	High

Table 1 presents the level of parenting behavior. The overall mean rating is 3.94 or high level. This means that students oftentimes feel the warmth, rejection, structure, chaos, autonomy support and coercion from their parents. Further, the students often feel loved and cared for by their parents. They also feel that they are rejected or unwanted and they see that rules in the house are oftentimes imposed to them. Moreover, they need help and often sure that their parents will keep their promises. They often feel that their parents try to control everything that they do and boss them around.

Table 2. *Level of Personality Traits of College Students*

Indicator	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Extraversion	0.56	4.02	High
Agreeableness	0.63	4.11	High
Conscientiousness	0.53	4.15	High
Neuroticism	0.75	3.78	High
Openness	0.67	4.20	High
Overall	0.44	4.05	High

Presented in Table 2 is the level of personality traits of college students and the obtained mean rating is 4.05 or high level. This means that most of the students often feel that they have a high level of extraversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, and openness, while having a low level of neuroticism, given that the statements regarding this indicator are positively constructed. Further, the students claim that they are often sociable and full of energy, helpful, considerate and kind towards almost everyone, feel that they are often organized, goal-oriented, and they work reliably, emotionally resilient and tend to a broad range of imagination and curiosity, as well as having a high level of creativity.

Table 3. *Significant Relationship between Parenting Behavior and Personality Traits of Students*

Parenting Behavior	Personality Traits					
	Extraversion	Agreeableness	Conscientiousness	Neuroticism	Openness	Overall
Warmth	.087 (.347)	.243* (.030)	.240* (.023)	.250* (.024)	.098 (.397)	.251* (.017)
Rejection	.136 (.221)	.286** (.004)	.326** (.000)	.322** (.001)	.214* (.043)	.361** (.000)
Structure	.163 (.122)	.198* (.047)	.009 (.955)	.102 (.311)	.103 (.309)	.158 (.117)
Chaos	.363*** (.000)	.241* (.016)	.330** (.001)	.263** (.008)	.172 (.087)	.370** (.000)
Autonomy Support	.138 (.171)	.108 (.284)	.272** (.006)	.082 (.420)	-.056 (.582)	.138 (.172)
Coercion	.268** (.007)	.134 (.184)	.103 (.307)	.190 (.058)	.136 (.177)	.228* (.023)
Overall	.326** (.000)	.326** (.001)	.338** (.001)	.354** (.001)	.195 (.056)	.431** (.000)

Presented in Table 3 is the correlation between parenting behavior and personality traits of college students with the overall r-value of .431 and a p-value which is lesser than 0.05 level of significance. The result is significant and thus, the rejection of the null hypothesis. This implies that personality traits of college students is dependent on the parenting behavior of their parents. Furthermore, parenting behavior has to do with the personality traits of the students.

It can also be gleaned from the table that there are indicators of parenting behaviors such as warmth; rejection; chaos; and coercion are directly related to the personality traits of college students. However, indicators such as structure and autonomy support are not related to personality traits of college students.

Generally, the hypothesis that *there is no significant relationship between parenting behavior and personality traits of college students* is rejected since both independent and dependent variables display a significant correlation.

Table 4. *Indicators of Parenting Behavior Best Predict Personality Traits of Students*

Parenting Behaviors	Personality Traits			
	Unstandardized Beta	Standardized Beta	T	Sig.
Warmth	0.11	.015	.118	.916
Rejection	0.98	.208	1.186	.245
Structure	0.87	.178	1.952	.093
Chaos	0.109	.219	1.324	.182
Autonomy Support	0.38	.053	.459	.650
Coercion	-.005	-.012	-.086	.984
R	.446			
R Square	.190			
F-Value	3.746			
P-Value	.003			

Table 4 presents that none of the indicators of parenting behavior best predict the personality traits of the students. The p values obtained by each indicator is greater than 0.05 level of significance. The result is not significant and thus, the acceptance of the null hypothesis. This implies that none of the indicator of parenting behavior can singly predict personality traits of college students. However, when the indicators of parenting behavior are combined, they garnered an overall r value of .446 with the R square value of .19 which means that parenting behavior indicators have significant influence by 19% to students' personality traits.

Moreover, the personality traits of college students is regressed by 19% of the combined indicators of parenting behavior. The variance of 81% are attributed to other factors not covered in the study. Nonetheless, as revealed in the F value of 3.746 with a p value 0.05 level of significance, the result is significant and thus, the rejection of the null hypothesis. This implies that parenting behavior significantly influence the personality traits of the students as revealed in the F value of 3.746. Parenting behavior has to do with the personality traits of the students. Consequently, personality traits are significantly affected by parenting behaviors.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the findings, the researcher concluded the level of parenting behavior of parents is high and the level of personality traits of the college students is also high. There is a significant relationship between parenting behavior of parents and personality traits of the college students. Conversely, parenting behavior of parents significantly influence the personality traits of the college students. However, none of the indicator of parenting behavior can singly predict personality traits of the college students.

This result same with the study by Jarzyna (2012) Personality traits such as, emotional stability, openness, and agreeableness to experience have been linked to family interactions that facilitate warm and supportive relating environment. These traits improve a parent's ability to recognize and respond to their child's different behaviors, which yields positive interaction between the parents and their children.

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